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Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security

An economic modellers' perspective

Executive summary

A joint paper by the Horizon Europe projects

ACT4CAP²⁷

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Land Management for Sustainability

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Further information

ACT4CAP27: Advancing Capacity and analytical Tools for supporting Common Agricultural Policies post 2027 | <https://act4cap27.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101134874>

BrightSpace: Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space | <https://brightspace-project.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060075>

LAMASUS: LAnd use and MAnagement modelling for SUStainable governance | <https://www.lamasus.eu/> | <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060423>

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Executive summary

New context. The European Union is facing unprecedented security and economic challenges. While the strategic importance of domestically produced food for security has been recognized in the Niinistö report, as well as in the 2025 European Commission's Vision for Agriculture and Food, which positions agriculture as a key strategic sector, the economic relevance of the sector seems to be neglected in the pivotal Draghi report on strengthening the EU's competitiveness. The primary agricultural sector alone indeed plays only a minor role in EU economic output, but this view ignores its crucial role for the development of important upstream industries and downstream food and bio-based value chains. Simultaneously, agriculture's environmental footprint, impact on natural resources, and climate-related challenges require sustained policy attention.

Background. Economic modelling has been providing robust quantitative science-based underpinning for Common Agricultural Policy development for decades. The models used by the European Commission have been continuously updated to represent evolving societal goals, socio-economic and political contexts, and environmental changes. Three Horizon Europe projects – ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS, which together sponsor this paper – are the most recent examples in this tradition. These projects were initialized three to five years ago in a markedly different (geo)political context. As they approach their final phase, including scenario-based policy impact assessments, this paper presents reflections by the project coordinators, senior scientists, and scientific advisors on new priority areas for analysis within these three projects linked to policy action that may fit the current context.

Aim of this paper. Given the urgent need to respond swiftly and strategically to multiple concurrent EU crises, this paper – drawing on the authors' extensive experience in economic modelling and policy analysis - reflects on the agrifood sector's potential to contribute meaningfully to EU competitiveness and economic growth. It identifies key leverage points to unlock these potentials, while fostering food security and environmental sustainability, providing guidance to the analytical work in the above-mentioned projects. The paper concludes by highlighting needed upgrades in the economic modelling capacities to ensure their continued ability to support policy makers in a rapidly changing environment.

Performance. The EU is more than self-sufficient in food, largely due to its internationally **competitive agrifood** sector. This competitiveness is driven by favourable climatic conditions, the use of advanced knowledge, innovation and management practices, integration into strong value chains, and access to global markets. The vast majority of the EU population is **food secure**. Nevertheless, around one in twelve EU residents cannot afford a protein-rich meal. Food production relies on numerous inputs, many of which - like animal feed and fertilizers - are imported. Food security is therefore partly **dependent on imports** and comes with a **significant environmental footprint**. In addition, farmers' incomes, which vary and fluctuate over time, remain under constant pressure due to rising input costs and their relatively weak position within the agrifood supply chain.

Economic opportunities exist throughout the **agrifood supply chain**, not only in the production of high-quality, safe and healthy food, but also in emerging sectors of the **(non-food)**

bioeconomy, such as construction materials, biochemicals, and bioenergy, where reducing import dependency is also possible. Although the EU is lagging behind global competitors in the **digital transition of the economy**, multiple applications of digital technologies in agriculture and related sectors could contribute to the necessary push, boosting innovation and strengthening EU competitiveness.

Enabling this progress requires both **innovations** and **policies that foster synergies between public and private sectors and different policy objectives**. **Five priority action areas (PAAs)** have been identified for their high potential for simultaneously boosting EU competitiveness, reinforcing EU and global food security, and reducing the environmental footprint of the agricultural sector. The three Horizon Europe projects mentioned above are well-positioned to assess the economic, social, and environmental impacts of policy measures within these PAAs:

PAA1. Fostering income and resilience through result-based policies that integrate economic and environmental performance. Newly available environmental observation systems may enable a shift from practice-based to result-based policies, providing farmers with the flexibility to develop strategies tailored to their specific situation. This approach helps maximizing synergies between economic and environmental performance, opens new markets for ecosystem services like nature farming, facilitates access to private funding, like carbon credits, and reduces administrative burden.

PAA2. Integrated nutrient management to enhance strategic autonomy. Reducing fertilizer use by mainstreaming precision farming technologies, promoting the production of alternative green fertilizers, and enhancing manure recycling, together with supporting domestic protein crop cultivation, has the potential to reduce both the need for fertilizers as well as feed imports, two critical dependencies in the agrifood sector. These measures can also create new income opportunities for farmers and their suppliers. At the same time, environmental pressures are alleviated.

PAA3. Enhancing the agrifood sector competitiveness and food security through level-playing field trade agreements. Strategically advancing bilateral and multilateral free trade agreements should be further pursued to create new opportunities for the competitive EU agrifood sector and contribute to global food security. At the same time measures need to be taken to prevent unfair competition that may undermine EU food security and social or environmental standards.

PAA4. Strengthening innovation leadership in the new bioeconomy. Enhanced support for research and development as well as technology diffusion at both the farm level and in downstream sectors will enable these sectors to benefit from new (non-food) markets emerging from the transition to a regenerative, fossil-free, circular economy. The bioeconomy is about balancing food and non-food applications of biomass on the one hand and the various needs within a society on the other, with sustainability and circularity as core principles. A robust carbon credits system can play a key role in the process of incentivizing sustainable practices and innovation.

PAA5. Democratizing digitalization to ensure agricultural sector attractiveness and technological innovation. The Common Agricultural Policy should evolve into a digitally enabled policy framework that promotes digitalization in both farming practices and

administration, driving and facilitating sustainable productivity growth and simplification. Capacity building, knowledge transfer, and targeted support, especially for small and medium-sized farms and enterprises, are essential to ensure that no one is left behind. Domestic digital solutions should be promoted to foster EU-led innovation and economic growth while helping to prevent the emergence of new critical dependencies.

Need for new economic modelling developments. The scientific economic modelling community stands ready to support the transition to a competitive, sustainable, circular, and resilient food system by providing tools that analyse the impact of policies and strategies and identify synergies and trade-offs between policy objectives, thus enhancing both effectiveness and efficiency of policy design. However, in light of the evolving geopolitical and economic context, further model developments are essential. Key areas for advancement include:

- Strengthening the connection between agro-economic and environmental modelling by enhancing the **integration and mutual processing of spatial input and output data** (Model-Data fusion).
- Elements of **Integrated Nutrient Management**, have to be enhanced in the modelling toolbox by enhancing **livestock** representation and including the production and adoption of green fertilisers, the use of precision agricultural technologies and (manure) **circularity practices**.
- Bilateral **trade** agreements modelling, including **sustainability provisions** and regulatory asymmetries in (bi- and multilateral) trade agreements.
- Full integration of the agrifood sector into the broader **bioeconomy** and enhanced representation of the **multiplier effects in both upstream and downstream sectors**.
- **Endogenizing knowledge and innovation processes**, including the role of **digitalization**. Identifying enablers of and barriers to **innovation adoption**, to add model parameters that better represent impacts of investments in technology on yields and other economic, social, and environmental indicators.
- Extending the modelling of shifting **consumer behaviour** by endogenizing changes in consumer preferences (e.g. protein transition) based on nudging behavioural change to better represent the potential impact of demand-side transformations.
- Representing **climate change impacts and adaptation**, including extreme weather events and dedicated adaptation options.

Sustainable agricultural sector: A key component of EU economic prosperity and security

An economic modellers' perspective

This joint paper, authored by leading economic modellers from the Horizon Europe projects ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS, presents a compelling case for placing a sustainable agricultural sector at the heart of the European Union's future prosperity and strategic autonomy. Arguing that "business as usual" is no longer an option, the paper outlines how agriculture, while only a small portion of the EU's GDP, underpins a vast and complex agri-food and bioeconomy network with significant multiplier effects. The authors stress, in line with the Draghi report that renewed political and investment efforts are needed to boost innovation, competitiveness, food security, and environmental resilience across the sector.

The paper introduces five Priority Action Areas (PAAs): fostering farm resilience through result-based policies, integrated nutrient management, boosting agri-food competitiveness through fair trade, leading innovation in the bioeconomy, and democratising digitalisation to ensure sector-wide inclusion. Each area is grounded in the premise that sustainable practices and technological advancements can drive both economic and ecological gains. The authors also underscore the urgency of maintaining the EU's global leadership in high-value food production while reducing critical dependencies on imported inputs like fertilisers and digital technologies.

Drawing on decades of experience in model-based policy assessment, the paper calls for a new generation of economic modelling tools to support the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and broader EU strategic goals post-2027. These include better integration of environmental and economic data, representation of nutrient cycles, full bioeconomy integration, modelling of innovation dynamics, and deeper analysis of shifting consumer behaviours and climate change adaptation. The collaboration among ACT4CAP27, BrightSpace, and LAMASUS exemplifies how research can offer rigorous, science-based insights to support policy design in an increasingly complex agri-food landscape.

The full paper is available for download from here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413131>

